

Effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape - scanning and experimental tests

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ABSTRACT

Thin-walled structures are popular with builders and designers in the automotive, aerospace, shipbuilding, and civil engineering industries. This is due to their high strength-to-low weight ratio. This paper analyses thin-walled I-section columns, which were formed by connecting back-to-back two channels with a modified cross-sectional shape. The fasteners were sheet metal screws. The columns were subjected to compression, and the boundary conditions used were intended to resemble support bilateral restraint with possible translation along the length of the column, respectively, according to the direction of the compressive force. Experimental tests were carried out, based on which graphs of compressive force as a function of deflection of the column web and as a function of column shortening were obtained. Based on the tests, the values of the ultimate load capacities (maximum forces) and the critical forces were determined. It was found that the more modified the shape of the cross section, the higher values of maximum forces and critical forces were obtained. In addition, reference was made to geometric imperfections, which were measured using a Coordinate Measuring Machine. It was found that in cross sections that have a greater number of bends, the values of deviations from the expected dimensions are much higher than for columns that have more classic cross-section shapes.

Keywords: buckling, compression, stability of structures, I-beams.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled cold-formed steel sections are a very popular member for building. These sections also find their use in the automotive, shipbuilding, or aerospace industries. Their primary advantage is their high strength relative to their low weight. Nowadays, the aim is to achieve the highest possible strength of thin-walled structures. To increase the strength of thin-walled sections, they can be reinforced with polymer carbon strips (1), but also their cross-sectional shapes can also be modified by adding various types of bends.

(2). The disadvantage of thin-walled structures is their nonresistance to loss of stability, which is difficult to estimate, and determining critical loads with high accuracy is a very difficult issue. In addition, thin-walled structures are particularly susceptible to geometric imperfections. In the analysis of thin-walled sections with modified cross-sectional shape, they must not be ignored, as they have a significant impact on their ultimate load capacity and buckling behaviour. Each additional bend has the potential for geometric imperfections.

This paper shows the experimental tests to which three types of thin-walled sections, made by joining back-to-back two channels with a modified cross-sectional shape, were subjected. The columns were connected by six sheet metal screws and subjected to compression.

Li et al. (3) subjected to experimental testing, numerical analysis, and theoretical analysis built-up sections formed by connecting two channels with sheet metal screws. The columns were loaded with a compressive force. They analysed the effect of assembly errors, fastener spacing on the

ultimate load capacity of the built-up members. Macdonald et al. (4) described channel sections having perforations on the web and on the flange. The channels were subjected to compression and experimental, numerical and theoretical methods were used for the study. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of perforations on the load carrying capacity and buckling behaviour of compressed sections. In the analysis of thin-walled sections, it is particularly important to validate the results obtained, so conducting tests with several methods is desirable and allows presenting meaningful results.

Craveiro et al. (5) analysed built-up closed sections formed by joining channel sections. The columns were loaded in compression. Their study highlighted geometric imperfections that they measured along the length of the built-up sections. In paper (6), they investigated the effect of local and global imperfections on the behaviour of thin-walled I sections fabricated by welding. The effect of geometric imperfection was found to be highly dependent on the nominal slenderness ratio of the columns. Couto and Vila Real (7) evaluated the effects of self-stressing and geometric imperfections of thin-walled I sections on their compressive strength. Zhang et al. (8) pointed out that geometric imperfections significantly affect the strength and resistance to loss of stability of thin-walled columns with non-standard cross-sectional shape. They used a 3D scanning technique to determine these imperfections.

The above work indicates that assessing the impact of imperfections on the behaviour of thin-walled structures is extremely important. This paper shows geometric imperfections that were measured using a Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM).

2 SUBJECT OF RESEARCH

The subjects of the research were thin-walled I columns with external cross-section dimensions of 80x80mm and a length of 1000mm. The columns are made of 0.5mm thick sheet metal using cold forming technology using manual or semi-automatic bending machines. The shapes of the analysed cross-sections and their dimensions are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Subject of the research

Sections are made of DX51 steel. The mechanical properties of this steel were determined in static tensile tests of flat samples cut from the steel sheet from which the columns were made. The tensile test was performed in accordance with the PN-EN ISO 6892-1 standard. The mechanical properties of DX51 steel are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of DX51 steel obtained on the basis of a static tensile test

Mechanical property	Symbol	Value
Young's modulus	E	181 GPa
Upper yield point	R_{eH}	330 MPa
Tensile strength	R_m	380 MPa

The I columns were created by connecting two C sections back-to-back. The connector consisted of sheet metal screws, the location of which is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Location of connectors (six sheet metal screws)

3 TEST STAND

Experimental tests were carried out in the Laboratory of the Department of Strength of Materials and Structures of the Poznan University of Technology. The ZWICK Z100/Roell universal testing machine with a measuring range of 0.2-100kN was used for the tests. To obtain the desired boundary conditions, a special test stand was designed and manufactured, shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Test stand

The lower support and upper support were designed so that three translations and three rotations were locked in the lower support, and two translations and three rotations were locked in the upper support. It was only possible to move the column along its length, so this was the direction corresponding to the compressive force. The support was implemented using two spacers that were twisted together in such a way as to prevent translation and rotation from occurring at the ends of the column.

The compressive force was applied by moving the crosshead of the test machine uniformly across the frontal cross section of the column. Three deflection sensors were used for the tests, the location of which is shown in part in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Location of deflection sensors

Sensors measured transverse strain/deflection on the web of compressed columns. Deflection sensors with a measurement range of 10mm were used.

4 CRITICAL FORCES AND ULTIMATE LOAD CAPACITY

On the basis of the experimental tests carried out, graphs of the compression force as a function of the shortening of the columns and the compression force as a function of the deflection of the web were obtained from the measurements of the deflection sensors.

The compression force as a function of the column shortening of the columns are shown in Figure 5. Based on these graphs, the ultimate load capacities of the columns, i.e. the maximum forces at which the failure of the columns occurred, were determined. The values of maximum forces, or ultimate load capacities, are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 5. Compression force as a function of column shortening

Table 2. Limiting load capacities of compressed columns

Column	Maximum force F_{max} [kN]
2T1	14.3
2T2	39.1
2T3	46.9

The highest load carrying capacity was obtained for column 2T3, the column with the most modified cross-sectional shape, with a value equal to 46.9kN. On the other hand, the lowest value was obtained for column 2T1, with a value equal to 14.3kN.

On the basis of the force diagrams as a function of web deflection, critical forces were determined. The averaged strain method was used to determine the critical force, as shown in Figure 6.

(a) Column 2T1

(b) Column 2T2

(c) Column 2T3

Fig. 6. Force as a function of average deflection - determination of critical force

The critical force was determined as the coordinate of the intersection point of the straight lines that approximate the pre-buckling state (orange) and the post-buckling state (grey). The critical force values are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Critical force values

Column	Critical force F_{cr} [kN]
2T1	5.01
2T2	10.04
2T3	18.45

The highest value of critical force was obtained for column 2T3, which was equal to 18.45kN. The lowest for column 2T1, as to value equal to 5.01kN.

5 GEOMETRIC IMPERFECTIONS

Geometric imperfections are a certain deviation from the expected shape of a given component. They arise from the manufacture of sections, during cold forming. Additionally, geometric imperfections can appear as a result of the occurrence of assembly errors.

The geometric imperfections of the sections analysed were measured using a CMM. Measurements were made in the cross sections indicated in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Geometric imperfections in eight cross-sections of column 2T1

The largest deviation of the dimension of the 2T1 column from the ideal dimension is 1.53mm.

Fig. 8. Geometric imperfections for columns 2T2 (Section P1) and 2T3 (section P8).

A similar analysis was performed for column 2T2, the largest dimension deviation for this column is 3.56mm. On the contrary, for column 2T3, it is 4.21mm, as shown in Figure 8. It can be seen from the above that the more modified the cross-sectional shape of the column, the higher the values of dimensional deviations.

Fig. 9. Local buckling of compressed columns

The compressed columns suffered a loss of stability. The webs and flanges showed half-waves, characteristic of local buckling, which are shown in Figure 9.

6 CONCLUSION

Table 4 shows a summary of the results obtained. Reference has been made to the weights of the columns. It was assumed that column 2T1, with the most classical cross-sectional shape, would be the base column to which the results and weights obtained for the other columns would be referred.

Table 4. Summary of results and reference to weight of columns

Column	Weight [kg]	F_{max} [kN]	F_{cr} [kN]
2T1	1.224	14.3	5.01
2T2	2.039	39.1	10.04
2T3	2.180	46.9	18.45
2T1/2T1	100%	1	1
2T2/2T1	166%	2.73	2.00
2T3/2T1	178%	3.28	3.68

- As the modification of the cross-sectional shape of the column increases, the value of the maximum force increases, and therefore the limit load capacity of the column increases. The highest value of maximum force was obtained for column 2T3. Similarly, in the case of the critical force, the highest value was also obtained for column 2T3.

- The lightest is the 2T1 column, and its weight is 1.224kg. On the other hand, the highest weight was obtained for column 2T3, which is equal to 2.180kg.
- The weight of the 2T2 column compared to the 2T1 column increases by 66%. The maximum force is 2.73 times higher and the value of the critical force for this column compared to the base column has doubled.
- The weight of the 2T3 column compared to the 2T1 column increases by 78%. Comparing the two columns in terms of the maximum force value, we get a 3.28 increase in this force. In contrast, the critical force increases 3.68 times.

The effect of geometric imperfections on the strength and resistance to loss of stability of compressed, thin-walled, I-beam columns will be shown in the work of Michal Plust, titled "The effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape". Effect of geometric imperfections on compression of back-to-back I-beam columns with modified cross-sectional shape - numerical study. The numerical analysis of columns with an ideal shape will be shown and compared with the results obtained in the FEA analysis for real sections whose surfaces were obtained from 3D scanning.

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